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MegaRoller

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Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

Collaborative project

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D6.14

Data management report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The scope of the MegaRoller Project has been to develop and demonstrate a Power Take-Off (PTO) for wave energy converters. During the project, MegaRoller has generated, collected, and reused various types of research data.

The purpose of the MegaRoller Data management report is to give an overview of the research data handling and infrastructure in this project, to indicate what research data sets were created or collected and what has been shared or will be shared with the public. This report is also a tool to explain the decisions on data handling made during the project.

The MegaRoller project is using the Zenodo repository to comply to H2020 Open Access Mandate, and data set underlying scientific publications and classified as public has been/will be uploaded to the MegaRoller community in Zenodo.

Each data set is given a persistent identifier (DOI), supplied with relevant metadata, and closely linked to MegaRoller grant number and project acronym. Publications and underlying research data are linked. Creative Common licences regulate reuse of the MegaRoller research data. Data security arrangements are defined for SINTEF SharePoint and the Zenodo repository. Ethical aspects affecting data sharing have been considered.

1 INTRODUCTION AND DATA SUMMARY

1.1 Purpose of the document

The MegaRoller Data management report is a formal document containing information concerning the handling of data during and after the finalization of the research project. The document indicates what research data sets were created or collected and what has been shared or will be shared with the public. This report is also a tool to explain and document the decisions on data handling made during the project.

1.2 List of definitions, acronyms, and abbreviations

BibTeX	is a reference management software for formatting lists of references.
CC licence	Creative Commons licences are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work.
CC-BY	This CC-license lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon your work, even commercially, as long as they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.
CSL	Citation Style Language is an open XML-based standard to format citations and Bibliographies.
DMP	Data management plan.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier.
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable data
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation is an open-standard file format.
MARCXML	MARCXML is an XML schema based on the common MARC21 standards.
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting.
Research data	Refers to information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings, and images.
REST API	REST is an architectural style that defines a set of constraints to be used for creating web Services. API means Application Programming Interface.
SSL/TLS	Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security are protocols offering secure communication on the internet.
Zenodo	Zenodo is a catch-all repository that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and

institutions to share research results, make research results citable and search and reuse open research results from other projects. Zenodo is harvested by the OpenAIRE portal.

1.3 Structure of this document

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 is an introduction chapter describing the main purpose of the Data management report and a data summary.
- Section 2 describes the main principles (FAIR) for the data management in this project and how MegaRoller has complied with the H2020 Open Access Mandate.
- Section 3 describes the allocation of resources.
- Section 4 gives a detailed description of data security arrangements.
- Section 5 deals with ethical aspects connected to data management in the MegaRoller project.

The tool DMPOnline, hosted by Data Curation Centre has been used generating this document. It is based on the Horizon 2020 DMP template.

1.4 Relationship with other deliverables

The Data management report is the final version of the MegaRoller Data management plan, a document evolving during the project lifetime:

- Deliverable D6.5 Data management plan (initial version, due month 6)
- Deliverable D6.19 Data management update (update, due month 18)

This document complements the following deliverables:

- D6.15 Communication report II
- D6.16 Dissemination report II

1.5 Summary of data

MegaRoller has been generating and reusing various types of data. The size of the data sets has been moderate and didn't represent any challenge regarding transfer, storage capacity or handling. A more detailed list of the actual data sets created in the project and its accessibility is given in Table 1.

1.6 Research data handling in MegaRoller

Every partner has been responsible for uploading the research data sets they have created or collected to the MegaRoller SharePoint site, and if classified as public, also to the MegaRoller community in Zenodo.

1.6.1 Versioning and File formats

Stored data sets in MegaRoller SharePoint site have used standard SharePoint version control. Zenodo offers version control of uploaded elements, assigning DOIs to every version of an uploaded file.

The MegaRoller data sets have various formats such as: txt, xls, pdf, ppt and others.

1.6.2 Upload instructions

The text box below and Figure 1 are the instructions given to partners for uploading elements to MegaRoller SharePoint site and Zenodo:

Upload instructions - MegaRoller SharePoint Site
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please upload all MegaRoller data sets to this folder in the MegaRoller SharePoint site: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 100 Research data • Use this naming convention (for details se 2.1.2): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Descriptive text H2020_MegaRoller_DeliverableNumber_UniqueDataNumber ○ Descriptive text H2020_MegaRoller_PublicationNumber_UniqueDataNumber • Be sure to use the same file name when uploading later versions • Register mandatory metadata on your data set by adding a new item to this list: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MegaRoller Research Data
Upload instructions - Zenodo
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data underlying scientific publications/classified as "Public" should, in addition, be uploaded to the MegaRoller Community in Zenodo. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create a profile in Zenodo to be able to upload files • Uploading should be done as soon as possible and at the latest on article publication. Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets created/collected by them. If needed task leader WP6.7 will supply assistance.

Figure 1 MegaRoller research results overview and upload instructions

2 FAIR DATA IN THE MEGAROLLER PROJECT

The MegaRoller project has been working according to the principles of **FAIR data** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.) The project has aimed to maximise access and reuse of research data generated by the project. At the same time, most data sets generated in this project cannot be shared due to commercial or IPR reasons. Table 1 gives details on the actual data sets created and their accessibility.

2.1 Findable data

MegaRoller has used Zenodo repository as the main tool to comply with the H2020 Open Access mandate. A MegaRoller community was established in the beginning of the project period, public deliverables have been uploaded and published. All scientific articles/papers and public data sets have been/will be uploaded to this community in Zenodo and enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number and Project Acronym. Each partner has been responsible for uploading the data sets that they have created or collected and to assign relevant keywords. Zenodo provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements.

2.1.1 Naming conventions

This is the naming convention used for MegaRoller research data:

- Descriptive text H2020_MegaRoller_DeliverableNumber_UniqueDataNumber
- Descriptive text H2020_MegaRoller_PublicationNumber_UniqueDataNumber

Example: RMS_simulation_H2020_MegaRoller_2.2_3

2.1.2 Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)

DOI's for public data sets has been assigned with the DOI functionality provided by Zenodo. DOI versioning is available to assign unique identifiers to updated versions of the data records.

2.1.3 Metadata in Zenodo

Metadata associated with each published data set is by default:

- Digital Object Identifiers and version numbers
- Bibliographic information
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information
- Access and licensing info
- Language

2.2 Accessible data

The H2020 Open Access Mandate aims to make research data generated by H2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protecting sensitive data due to commercial or security reasons. Public data sets from the MegaRoller project have been/will be uploaded to Zenodo, and made open, free of charge. Publication and underlying data sets have been/will be linked through persistent identifiers, using the Related identifiers function in Zenodo. Data sets with dissemination level "Confidential" will not be shared due to commercial exploitation.

Metadata including licences for individual data records as well as record collections will be harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application. Information on needed software tools to access the MegaRoller data sets will be provided. The table below provides a list of all data sets generated in the MegaRoller project and their accessibility.

Table 1 Datasets generated in the MegaRoller project, and their accessibility

Task	Description/Name of data	Purpose	Format	Origin (Lead)	Class	Comments
1.1	Wave prediction at MegaRoller installation site	Specify the wave characteristics at MegaRoller installation site for power performance and load estimation	zip	UiB	PU	Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5769735
1.6	MegaRoller Test Bench Assembly CTI plan	Test Bench CTI	pdf	CAT	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
2.1	MEGAROLLER WP2 Charging level measurement method 19.05.2020	Determine the charging method for the PTO	ppt	Hydroll	CO	The method could be patented. After patent, it will be public but not before. Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
2.1	Conceptual and detailed hydraulic design	To find hydraulic components	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D2.1
2.2	Conceptual electrical design	To find electrical components for PTO system and electric distribution	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial reason and Security reasons Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D3.4
2.2	MegaRoller near-shore wave data	WP2, Task 2.2, MegaRoller near-shore wave data	txt	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
2.3	Conceptual and detailed mechanical design	Twin drive train innovation	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D2.5
2.4	Conceptual and detailed control system design	Control system design	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D2.3

2.5	Preliminary Life Cycle Assessment report	Environmental and socio-economic acceptance of the project	pdf	WavEC	CO	Data confidentiality reasons regarding the LCA Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D2.4
2.5	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and socio-Economic impact Assessment (SEIA) models	Environmental and socio-economic acceptance of the project	pdf	WavEC	PU	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D2.6 Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3372479
3.1	Hydraulic components	Hydraulic implementation	pdf	Hydroll	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services) Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D3.5
3.2	Datasheet_ABB HES880_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_1.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Product manual HES880-104 converter modules	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_ABB WaterCooledMotors_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_2.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet Low voltage Water cooled motors	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_ABB_3GZF500628-188_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_3.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Dimension print WATER COOLED SQUIRREL CAGE MOTOR WITH TB 370, SPECIAL SHAFT, SPECIAL BEARINGS, BEARING FANS AND ENCODER (L&L 600)	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Hydac 3966468_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_4.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2, Hydac HEX ZH802-110-00/G2 female	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data

3.2	Datasheet_Hydac e7112-4-03-12_NF_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_5.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Technical specifications, Inline filters	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Hydac E7619-2-07-14_MCS1000_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_6.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Technical specifications, Metallic contamination sensor	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Hydac e18061-4-11-13_ens3000_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_7.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2, Technical specifications, Electronic level switch	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Hydac e18302-1-0-11-13_ets4100_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_8.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2, Technical specifications, Electronic temperature transmitter	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Hydac e18326-2-11-13_hda7446_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_9.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2, Technical specifications, Electronic pressure transmitter	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Hydac e18331-2-11-13_ews3100_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_10.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Technical specifications, Electronic Flow Rate Transmitter	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Hydac HDA3840_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_11.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Technical specifications, Electronic Pressure Transmitter	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Hydman CAD Cartridge Valves_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_12.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet CAD Cartridge Valves	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data

3.2	Datasheet_IFM CR2031_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_13.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Device manual Output module compact module metal	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Kolmeks MVV6B-1-26_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_14.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet MVV6B	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Leine Linde IHA 607_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_15.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet Encoder model IHA 607	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_LEM cv 3-1500_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_16.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet Voltage Transducer CV 3-1500	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_LEM If 505-se_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_17.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet Current transducer LF 505-S	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Rexroth A4CSG_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_18.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet Axial piston variable pump A4CSG Series 3x	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_Rexroth A6VLM_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_19	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet Axial piston variable motor A6VM Series 63	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.2	Datasheet_TR electronic K-LMP30-SSI-1_H2020_MegaRoller_3.2_20.pdf	WP3, Task 3.2 Datasheet Linear-Transducer LMP30 - SSI	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.3	Mechanical components	Mechanical components	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D3.3

3.4	Wave height/ MegaRoller panel movement prediction Sea state 1 data Sea state 2 data Sea state 3 data Sea state 4 data	Control system implementation	txt	AWE	CO	Public data sharing requires approval from the consortium. 4 datasets Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
3.4	Control system implementation	Control system software	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D3.6
3.5	Handover meeting report	Hand-over to capture assembly requirements	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D3.2
4.1	Health & safety risk assessment report		pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D4.1
4.2	CTI, safety and quality assurance plans (PTO)		pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D4.2
4.3	MegaRoller PTO Assembly CTI Plan	WP4, T4.3 MegaRoller PTO Assembly CTI plan	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
4.4	Assembly instructions and order	Assembly work	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D4.4
5.2	PTO performance and power quality validation results	Validation of PTO	pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D5.5
5.2	PTO performance and power quality validation results, Report	Contrast the experimental results with the simulated ones.	pdf	VTT, ABB	CO	To be uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D5.4
5.3	Specification - Mechanism and hull load cycles	Basis for PTO design and reliability analysis	xlsx	VTT	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data The validation methodology and possible / available data sources are presented in the MegaRoller

						deliverable D5.1. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5749405
5.4	Final LCA report and Environmental Impact Assessment of the MegaRoller device	Evaluation of the socio-economic impacts of the project	pdf	WavEC	PU	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables D5.3 Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5749475
5.5	LCC data	Estimation of life cycle cost of the MegaRoller device		VTT	CO	Data used for both simulations and calculations is collected partly from public sources and partly confidential information from AWE. Stored by AWE
6.3	Innovation management plan		pdf	AWE	PU	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D6.2 Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2559185
6.3	Innovation management report incl. IPR Registry I		pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D6.9
6.3	Innovation management report incl. IPR Registry II		pdf	AWE	CO	To be uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D6.17
6.4	MegaRoller time-series of electricity production	WP6, Task 6.4 Find new opportunities and potential users of the MegaRoller project technologies. Reference: D6.12 Business cases, ch. 4	txt	SINTEF	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data

6.4	Metadata description	WP6, Task 6.4 Metadata description for time-series of electricity production data	txt	SINTEF	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data
6.5	Exploitation plan draft		pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D6.4
6.5	Exploitation plan update I and II		pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D6.10 + D6.18
6.5	LCOE report		pdf	AWE	PU	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D6.11 Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5749481
6.5	Business cases		pdf	AWE	PU	To be uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D6.12 and Zenodo
6.6	Description of the existing standards and their applicability. Gap analysis matrix	Assesses the salient gaps in certification related to the specifics of the technology. Useful for Technology developers considering a certification process; standardisation work groups; certification bodies	pdf	K2M	PU	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D6.6 Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3698879
7.1	Project Quality Handbook		pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D7.1
7.1	Project management plan		pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D7.2

7.1	Project management report I and II		pdf	AWE	CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D7.3 + D7.4
7.1	Final (Public) Report		pdf	AWE	PU	To be uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D7.5 To be uploaded to Zenodo
8.1	Project coordination plan		pdf		CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D8.1
8.2	Project coordination update		pdf		CO	Uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D8.2
8.3	Project coordination report		pdf		CO	To be uploaded to SharePoint Deliverables, D8.3
several	Data_for_value_of_energy_analysis_H2020_MegaRoller_10.1049ipc.2021.1383.zip	Dataset for analysis of the value of energy for wave, wind and solar power	zip	SINTEF	PU	Uploaded to SharePoint folder 100 Research Data Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5767455

2.3 Interoperable data

Zenodo uses JSON schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other formats such as Dublin Core, MARCXML, BibTeX, CSL, DataCite and export to Mendeley. The data record metadata will utilise the vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Reference to any external metadata is done with a resolvable URL.

2.4 Reusable data

The MegaRoller project has enabled third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) all public data sets, and regulate this by using Creative Commons Licences.

2.4.1 Recommended Creative Commons (CC) licences

Creative Commons licences are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. As a default, the CC BY license has been applied for public MegaRoller data. This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you.

2.4.2 Availability of the MegaRoller research data sets

For data published in scientific journals, the underlying data was made available as soon as possible after publication, although there were some delays due to the Covid-19 pandemic restrictions and remote work. The data sets have been linked to the publication by using related identifier in Zenodo. Data associated with public deliverables will be shared once the deliverable has been approved by the EC.

Open data can be reused in accordance with the Creative Commons licences. Data classified as confidential will not be reusable due to commercial exploitation.

The public data will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN. If Zenodo is phased out, data/metadata will be transferred to other appropriate repositories.

3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

MegaRoller has been using standard tools and a free of charge repository. The costs of data management activities have been limited to project management costs and will be covered by the project grants.

SINTEF Energi AS has been the lead for MegaRoller WP 6 Dissemination, Standardization & Exploitation, by WP leader Hans Christian Bolstad. Laila Økdal Aksetøy (SINTEF) has been the MegaRoller Data Manager and the curator for MegaRoller community in Zenodo.

4 DATA SECURITY, ACCESSABILITY AND LONGTERM STORAGE.

In this chapter, the security issues of the research data infrastructure in the MegaRoller project are explained.

4.1 Data security as specified for SINTEF SharePoint site

SINTEF SharePoint has been the working/collaboration area for the MegaRoller project during active project period. A dedicated folder for research data sets was established, and a dedicated list for collecting relevant metadata for each dataset.

The MegaRoller SharePoint site has these security settings:

- Access level: Restricted to persons (project members only)
- Encryption with SSL/TLS protects data transfer between partners and SINTEF SharePoint site
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevents or registers possible manipulation of data

Documents and elements in SINTEF SharePoint sites are stored in Microsoft's cloud solutions - in Ireland and the Netherlands. There is no use of data centres in the US or outside EU/EEA (Norway, Iceland or Switzerland).

Nightly back-ups are handled by SINTEF's IT operations contractor.

External access to the MegaRoller SharePoint site will be shut down per 2023-02-28. All project data will be stored for 10 years according to SINTEF ICT policy.

4.2 Data security as specified for Zenodo

Zenodo was chosen as the MegaRoller repository. All scientific publications, public deliverables, and public research data set have been uploaded to the MegaRoller community in Zenodo and made open accessible for everyone.

These are the security settings for Zenodo:

- Versions: Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and record are preserved.
- Replicas: All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.
- Retention period: Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
- Functional preservation: Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.
- File preservation: Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple

copies in the online system.

- Fixity and authenticity: All data files are stored along with an MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.
- Succession plans: In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

Public project results published in MegaRoller community in Zenodo will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years.

5 ETHICS

No ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data sharing were identified during the project period.

5.1 Personal data and GDPR compliance

Besides e-mail addresses, no personal data was identified in the MegaRoller project.

An e-mail address is personal data and covered by GDPR. The e-mail addresses of project participants are stored in the MegaRoller SharePoint site. Only the project participants invited will have access. The e-mail address is a prerequisite to access the projects working area. By accepting the SharePoint invitation, the participants consent to use and storage of e-mail address.

The email addresses will be deleted when external access to the project area is closed, 2023-02-28.

SINTEF has signed GDPR data processing agreements with both Microsoft and the IT operations contractor handling the SharePoint platform.